

1 **A gene whose mutation results in familial diarrheal disease is activated in inflammatory bowel**
2 **disease.**

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7 We describe here a gene whose mutation results in familial diarrheal disease is activated in inflammatory
8 bowel disease, *GUCY2C*. Guanylate activation indicated inflammasome induction in active Crohn's
9 Disease. GBP family activation was also prominent.

10 Citations

11 1. Fiskerstrand, T., Arshad, N., Haukanes, B.I., Tronstad, R.R., Pham, K.D.C., Johansson, S., Håvik,
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13 an activating GUCY2C mutation. New England Journal of Medicine, 366(17), pp.1586-1595.
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